

SERVICES FAIRNESS: AN ASSESSMENT OF THE BENIN ELECTRICITY DISTRIBUTION COMPANY IN BENIN METROPOLIS, EDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated customers' perception of procedural fairness in Benin Electricity Distribution Company (BEDC) service delivery in the Benin metropolis. The study adopted a survey-type research design. The instruments used for the primary data collection were a structured type of research questionnaire and a personal interview guide. To collect the required data for the study, a sample size of 250 respondents was selected using the snowball random sampling technique. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that customers' perception of BEDC services delivery from 2013 to 2024 was poor, procedurally unfair and below the stipulated electricity regulatory standards. Based on the findings, the study highlighted the need for BEDC to improve its operational efficiency, review its customer service policies and procedures, and become more transparent by making all the necessary working materials available to its employees, as doing this will make them effective and enable them to address all customer complaints fairly.

Keywords: Customer Perception, Service Fairness, Electricity Distribution Company, Benin Metropolis

Introduction

Since 2013 when the energy sector in Nigeria was privatized to enhance efficiency in service delivery and attract private investments (Okozi et al, 2022), eighteen (18) companies now make up the energy sector of the country and they are in the following order: 6 generating companies, one transmission company and 11 distributing companies (Ayamolowo et al, 2019). One of the electricity distribution companies (DisCo) is the Benin Electricity Distribution Company (BEDC) Plc. BEDC retails energy and operates in four States namely Delta, Edo, Ekiti and Ondo States, all in the Southern part of Nigeria. As of September 2023, BEDC operates 27 business districts, 350 offices and has 1,291,181 customers paying bills (Esan et al, 2024).

The role of BEDC, like other electricity distributing companies, is to provide connections and deliver electric energy to users at a level of service quality consistent with the applicable standards. Procure ancillary services, ensure proper metering at all connection points, and handle network emergencies as well as restore the network to its normal conditions safely and functionally (Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) - Distribution System/Code, Version 02 (n.d)). With these service mandates, the customers' perception becomes an inevitable outcome of the customer-firm relationship that is worthy of investigation. Therefore, gathered data about BEDC services fairness in the past eleven years will be proper for information and reforms, where necessary.

Fairness of measures, processes and procedures that determine the outcomes of exchange is termed procedural fairness (Lind, 2001). Procedural fairness, also known as procedural justice, is the quality of interpersonal treatment people receive, and the fairness of the procedures used to make decisions (Tyler, 1990, in Meyerson et al, 2021). In public policy, fairness is an ethical obligation to take the plurality of social values, perspectives and interests into account coherently and transparently (Giuseppe, 2017). Besides, in nature, if the individual is to be satisfied in a relationship, there must be a fair input/output balance (Ferguson et al, 2014) and is the expectation of customers to a service provider like BEDC. Therefore, service fairness is the customer's perception of justice in a service firm's behaviour or the customer's acuity of the degree of rightfulness in the conduct of a service organization (Seiders & Berry, 1998; Su & Hsu, 2013).

There is no doubt that people desire to have access to an uninterrupted or reliable power supply and accurate metering of energy supplied to them by BEDC, and, like in any other business transaction, the people understand and agree on what is fair and what is not fair (Anderson & Simester, 2010). This implies that customers' judgment of service fairness arises when their experience is compared to their fairness standards and they identify themselves as being either fairly or unfairly treated (Seiders & Berry, 1998). Also, by following the fairness theory, costs are expected to match with benefits in the process of social exchange and the exchange process people always evaluate the process of services delivery and its outcome and if the benefits match their cost, they consider such services as fair and react to the firm positively (Crisafulli & Singh, 2016). Therefore, services fairness in organisations like BEDC is the customer's assessment of whether the services provided compared to the bills they are to pay is reasonable, acceptable, and justifiable (Xia et al, 2004. Xiaoyun Han et al, 2019) and this has been found to impact certain business

contexts Jap & Anderson, 2003) including service quality (Giovanis et al, 2015), customers satisfaction and psychological empowerment (Han et al, 2019), customers loyalty (Kwortnik & Han, 2011), behavioural intentions (Su & Hsu, 2013), and customer-firm relationship (Liang et al, 2017). While these studies examined the impact of fairness in service delivery, the task of this study is to examine the extent to which BEDC, a service provider, has been procedurally fair in Benin Metropolis. The specific objective is to:

- (i). Assess the extent of procedural fairness in the BEDC service delivery pattern in Benin Metropolis

Literature Review

Procedural Fairness about Service Delivery

In a study of this nature, procedural fairness is usually interpreted based on social norms. According to Maxwell (2008), distributive fairness and procedural fairness are the two aspects of social fairness that consumers use to evaluate the overall price fairness. Thus, procedural fairness and distributive fairness are distinct assessments that bring about an overall assessment of the fairness of a price (Ferguson et al, 2014). Since the objective of the study is to ascertain service fairness, a three-order three-factor scale model - procedural fairness, price fairness and distributive fairness out of the five dimensions measurement model of service fairness that was developed by Shueh-Chin Ting (2013) in the context of the consumer-retailer relationship is adopted. By following Shueh-Chin Ting (2013), procedural fairness means BEDC process and procedures for service delivery are fair, price fairness means that the cost (monthly bills) sent to unmetered consumers is fair, and procedural fairness means that the (outcome) quality of services provided to the customers is fair. Taken together, procedural fairness is the customers' perception of whether or not the services of a service provider like BEDC are fair or free from bias and consistent with the expected standards. Procedural fairness is the quality of the interpersonal treatment customers receive from a service provider and the fairness of the procedures used to make decisions that affect the customers (Tyler, 1990, in Meyerson et al, 2021).

By following Tyler (1990), the four questions to answer before one can describe, for instance, the BEDC services delivery pattern as procedurally fair are: Are they trustworthy? Do they respectfully treat their customers? Are they neutral? Do they listen to the voices of their customers? According to Tyler (1990), BEDC will only be seen as trustworthy to the customers if they are sincere in their dealings by being helpful, honest and open and act consistently and in the best interests of customers. They will be seen as respectful when BEDC employees show respect for people's rights and exemplify dignified and polite treatment. This is crucial because it has been observed that people are particularly sensitive to positive signs when they are being treated respectfully and respond negatively to signs of rude behaviour (Meyerson et al, 2021). BEDCs will be seen as neutral when they treat all individuals and groups in the community equally and refrain from acting on biases or pre-existing views about people when making decisions. For instance, if for some reason an area enjoys constant electricity power supply while other areas

experience epileptic power supply or some others don't have electricity supply at all but are expected by BEDC to pay their monthly bills, treating people with unequal access is discriminatory; and this kind of action will portray BEDC as biased or not neutral (Tyler & Wakslak, 2004). Finally, that the customer's voice is heard means that the customers have a say in decisions that affect them. This includes having the opportunity to express concern or explain one's side of the story to the BEDC management team before decisions are taken, and when this is possible, it is an indicator of procedural justice (Adopted from Meyerson et al, 2021).

Electricity Distribution Companies' Service Delivery Issues in Nigeria

Studies have shown that despite efforts so far made to enhance access to electricity in Nigeria, millions of people still lack a dependable power supply (Esan et al, 2024). The services provided by the electricity distributing companies (DisCos) have been described as poor, and in some communities, it has been observed that BEDC, for instance, supply some of its customers with less than one hour of electricity per day (Egbejule, 2023). Similarly, Ikwuagwu & Ajah (2023) found out that there has been low power distribution by the DisCos in the country, where access exists with frequent blackouts. Despite the low power distribution, there is the unabated problem of using the estimated billing system, having many unmetered customers, the difficulty of having an energy supply-demand balance, as well as a lack of aggregate consumption data for facilities and residential homes (Oseni, 2015). What is more, despite the Electric Power Sector Reform Act (Amendment) bill of 2018 prohibiting and criminalizing the use of an estimated billing system, there has been continuous use by the DisCos to the extent that they now have many more unmetered customers and customers with meters that are unread (Ofonyelu & Eguabor, 2014; Audu et al, 2017). This has been described as unfavorable, unjust and ineffective metering systems (Fiasorgbor et al, 2022; Babatunde et al, 2023). Though many customers are willing to adopt the prepaid metering (PPM) system because of the unnecessary stress associated with the unread analogue meters they are either not available or available and given under unscrupulous conditions (Oseni, 2015). The result of these includes customer dissatisfaction (Arimoro, 2019; Emeter, 2021), illegal and corrupt practices like non-payment by public and private consumers for energy consumed, energy theft, constant and frequent clashes between distributing companies' employees and customers (Aremu, 2019; Soyemi, 2021). On this view, Akorede et al (2017) assert that about 50% of the power generated in the country is lost due to the combined effect of illegal consumption and unpaid unmetered customers estimated monthly bills.

In addition to the above, the National Bureau of Statistics report from 2015 to 2020 suggests that the activities of BEDC were characterized by unethical conduct, profit maximization and unfair treatment to customers. For instance, the energy distributed within the period by the DisCos was described as low and unstable, but the revenue generated from both metered and unmetered customers continues to increase within the said period. The number of estimated bill customers rose from 3.85 million in 2015 to 6.86 million in 2020, while the number of metered customers remained stable. It increased from 3.15 million in 2015 to 3.80 million in 2019, but reduced to 3.51 million in 2020.

Similarly, Okpare (2010) found that out of the over 180 million people in Nigeria, only 32 million households are connected to the National Grid and out of these, only 4 million households are consumers with active electric meters. This shows that it appears that there has been a deliberate attempt to slow down customers' metering process over the years and this cannot be said to be fair to the customers especially as this negates NERC guidelines number (f) which stipulates that there should be proper metering of all connection points to network and as Soyemi et al (2021) put it, in terms of meters availability and power distribution, the DisCos have not been fair to the customers. In their study, Ofonyelu & Eguabor (2014) found that irregularities in unmetered electricity billing systems are higher than in prepaid meter users. Similarly, Anyaehie et al (2018) compared the electricity bills of two consumers in an estate in Owerri, Imo state; one on prepaid meter and the other on estimated billing system and found out that, on average, consumers with pre-paid meters had lower bills than the unmetered consumers. About 80% of customers' complaints to the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) have been on poor energy distribution, non-justifiable monthly bills or overestimated bills and poor metering infrastructure (Arimoro et al, 2019).

Considering the above literature review and the deductions, the null hypothesis is stated to guide the study.

Ho¹ There is no procedural fairness in the BEDC services delivery pattern in the Benin metropolis

Theoretical Framework

This study is based on equity and institutional theory. Equity theory was developed by the psychologist John Stacey Adams in 1963 (Adams, 1963), originally for application in the organizational context. Equity theory helps to explain an individual's perception of fairness in any social exchange or relationship, based on the perception of one's input into the relationship and the output of those relations (Davlembayeva & Alamanos, 2023). Equity propose that individuals that are in a relationship who feel that they are getting more or less than what they have been given or offered to the other partner will feel guilty and some who are offering more than they receive will feel being used in that relationship, and this may lead to an end of the relationship (Disley, et al, 2009) This means that equity theory is based on people beliefs that they deserve a fair treatment in any interaction, and every person has his or her perception and notion of fairness. Therefore, in this study, equity is interpreted as justice in the form of distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice. However, for this study, procedural justice is conceived as the customers' perception of fairness in the BEDC pattern of energy distribution, metering and billing systems.

Several scholars across various disciplines, including sociology, organizational theory, and economics, such as Max Weber, Emile Durkheim, Talcott Parsons, Philip Seiznick, John Meyer and Brian Rowan have contributed to the development of institutional theory. Institutional theory has become a prominent framework for understanding organizational behaviour, social change and institutional dynamics. For instance, John Meyer and Brian Rowan in their 1977 study noted that organizations conform to social expectations for legitimacy and not necessarily for

economic rationality. And that norms, values, and regulations of institutions play laudable roles in shaping individuals and organizational behaviour. To Chowdhury (2021), institutional theory expects organizations to comply with external or social norms, rules, and requirements to receive legitimacy and support. This can be interpreted as, for example, BEDC is expected to comply with NERC rules and regulations as one of the DisCos in the country or for legitimacy and also as a subset of the society BEDC is expected to work with some set of values (including fairness), norms, and assumptions which constitute a reasonable economic behaviour (Arif Khan, 2022). This is apparently why Chowdhury (2021) maintains that other than conformity, institutional theory helps to bridge the gap between an organization's actions and societal expectations.

Taken together, the focus of equity theory and institutional theory is on social context in which individuals and organizations find themselves and operate, they are concerned with issues of fairness and legitimacy using different approaches. In spite of the differences in approach, both theories emphasize the importance of understanding human behaviour and decision-making in social contexts and therefore, they are considered appropriate for the study. However, since the unit of analysis of equity theory is on the individual-level, it constitutes the main theory in which this study is based as against the institutional theory whose unit of analysis can be more than the individual level to organizations and institutions, including government, market, culture and religion.

Research Methods

This study adopted a survey-type research design. The population of the study is all the adults in Benin City and its environs. However, in the absence of the total number of people living in the study area for research, the snowball random sampling technique was used to select fifty (50) respondents each from the five local government areas that make up the Benin metropolis namely Oredo, Egor, Ovia North –East, Orhionmwon and Ikpoba –Okha to arrive at a total of two hundred and fifty (250) respondents that was used for the study. The major instrument used for primary data collection was a self-designed structured personal interview guide and the research questionnaire. The instruments were designed in two sections: Section A and B. Section A was designed to collect demographic data of respondents while, section B consisted of eighteen (18) items on a three-order three-factor scale namely procedural fairness, price fairness and distributional fairness adopted from Shueh-Chin Ting (2013) five dimensions measurement model of service fairness developed in the context of exchange was used. The level of response to the items in the instruments was in the four-point Likert Scale format, namely: Strongly Agree [SA]; Agree [A], Disagree [D], and Strongly Disagree [SD], and these were sequentially weighted as 4, 3, 2 and 1, respectively. The methods used for data collection were electronic and manual, and thereafter, the data collected were analyzed using the weighted mean score. To determine the mean score, the weighted score of each level item was calculated and the total was divided by the number of respondents' responses on each item. A mean score of 2.50 and above was adopted as the criterion for measuring agreement/disagreement with the opinion variable on the scale.

Data Analysis

To examine BEDC service fairness, the items were raised in a three-order three-factor model of service fairness, namely procedural, price and distributive fairness. The weighted mean scores of responses to the items are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Distribution of Customers' Perception of BEDC Service Fairness

SN	Items	Mean Score	Remarks
1	The process of working with BEDC staff is generally fair	3.84	Agree
2	The activities of BEDC staff are conducted without bias	3.75	Agree
3	The processes in which BEDC staff use to meet customer needs is fair	1.84	Disagree
4	The procedures used by BEDC staff are consistent across customers	1.96	Disagree
5	I can appeal should I feel mistreated during service procedures	4.8	Agree
6	The installation or replacement of the transformer service process is smooth	1.96	Disagree
7	Waiting time for installation or replacement/repair of transformers is reasonable	2.00	Disagree
8	There are many unmetered customers, and the monthly bills sent to them are reasonable	1.64	Disagree
9	In many cases, customers pay for transformer replacement/repair, oil replacement, cables and other parts used for the repairs of faulty lines	4.8	Agree
10	BEDC staff expect payment for rendering maintenance and repair services	4.75	Agree
11	The cost of pre-paid meters and the conditions attached if people want to swap their analogue meters for pre-paid meters are fair and acceptable	1.84	Disagree
12	BEDC pre-paid meters are easily accessible in Delta State, but customers in Edo cannot buy from Delta and use them in Edo State	4.60	Agree
13	BEDC staff produce desired results for all customers without bias of any kind	1.40	Disagree
14	BEDC staff deliver good outcomes for all customers, regardless of who they are	1.64	Disagree
15	I can get the same outcomes as others do if I can pay the price	3.75	Agree
16	BEDC staff provided me service amount same as I expected	1.60	Disagree
17	BEDC staff delivers the promised service accurately the first time	1.65	Disagree
18	BEDC staff provided me with service quality similar as I expected	1.48	Disagree

Results in Table 1 show the weighted mean score of respondents' responses. Responses to items one (1) to seven (7) show that the majority agree that the process of working with BEDC employees is generally fair and also that their activities are conducted without bias and customers can appeal if unfairly treated, but they disagree on the process of meeting customers' needs including inconsistencies in processes involving transformer installations, replacement and repairs as well as the time it takes BEDC to fix faulty transformers and lines. This finding affirms the National Bureau of Statistics report (2015 – 2020) and the findings of scholars like Ofonyelu &

Eguabor (2014), Audu et al (2017) that the activities of BEDC were characterised by corruption, unethical conduct and unfair treatment to customers.

On the extent to which the cost of energy consumed is fair most especially to unmetered customers (items eight (8) to twelve (12) reveal that the majority agree that their monthly bills were outrageous and unfair. Also, they indicated that the cost of changing from analogue meters to pre-paid meters was high. While supporting this view, some of the respondents interviewed stated that in their attempt to change from analogue meters to pre-paid meters, they were requested to pay up many years of accumulated estimated bills (including the period their communities had a faulty transformer and never had electricity) which amount to hundreds of thousands of naira. Similarly, the majority agree that it was unreasonable, abnormal and unfair for pre-paid meters to be accessible in Delta State but difficult to access in Edo, and customers cannot buy from Delta and use them in Edo State. The majority also agree that BEDC employees, in many cases, cause customers with electricity supply issues to buy their transformers, replace/repair faulty ones including the cables and other parts needed for such repairs. Explaining this view, some of the respondents interviewed stated that whenever there are issues including transformer failure, theft and faulty lines they are usually told to wait and that they are working on it but after some time they are advised (on anonymous conditions) to contribute money as a group to solve such problems, as it will take a longer period before their head office can respond to such demands. This shows that the customers are compelled to fix such problems for BEDC. These findings are consistent with the reviewed literature such as Okpare et al (2010), Oseni (2015), Soyemi et al (2021) who found that the services delivery and metering systems used by the DisCos are services and facilities poor including having many unmetered customers and those with meters but are not read and are billed monthly.

On distributive fairness or the outcome of BEDC services delivery, responses to items thirteen (13) to eighteen (18) reveal that the majority agree that they can get the same outcome as others if only they can pay for such services and that their services are poor and biased in favour of certain areas. Those interviewed indicated a lack of neutrality on the part of BEDC. According to them, daily the built-up areas and the central business district usually have electricity supply for about twelve (12) hours but others in interior locations are supplied electricity for less than five (5) hours in three days, and in the same city some communities due to faulty lines or equipment's may not even have electricity supply for months.

This finding aligns with the reviewed literature, which highlights significant deficiencies in BEDC's electricity supply. For instance, Egbejule's (2023) study found that some customers receive less than an hour of electricity supply per day, while Ikwuagwu & Ajah (2023) study found frequent blackouts despite existing access. Similarly, Fiasorgbor et al (2022) and Babatunde et al (2023) describe BEDC's services as marred by poor power distribution, inadequate metering systems, and inequitable service delivery. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis is upheld, leading to the conclusion that BEDC's service delivery in the Benin metropolis since 2013 has lacked procedural fairness. This has notable implications for customer-firm relationships in an era where uninterrupted power supply is both an expectation and a necessity.

Conclusion

This study has shown that, despite the well-documented benefits of service fairness for both customers and providers, BEDC's service delivery in the Benin metropolis has been unfair since 2013. By employing a three-factor model: procedural, price, and distributive justice, this research contributes to the existing literature on service fairness while highlighting practical implications for trust and accountability within BEDC. The findings underscore the importance of fair service practices, not only to enhance customer satisfaction but also to foster trust in the organization. Upholding fairness in service delivery is essential for strengthening the customer-provider relationship and ensuring long-term business sustainability.

Recommendations

Considering the discussions and conclusions drawn in this study, there is a need for the management of BEDC to review its current customer service policies and procedures to identify areas that require improvement and develop new policies and procedures that would ensure fairness and transparency in service delivery.

Recognizing the essential nature of BEDC services to its numerous customers, there is the need for the management of BEDC to ensure that their staffs are well equipped with the necessary materials including effective means of movement, cable/wires, ladder, meters and transformer's to provide excellent customer service and also to be able to address customers' complaints fairly.

It is also suggested that there is need for BEDC to have an effective customer relationship management (CRM) system to better manage her customer interactions. What is more, efforts should be made to increase the number of hours of energy supply to the people of the area as this could help raise revenue generation drive and minimize customer complaints. Finally, noting the positive role of technology in contemporary times, there is a need for BEDC management to consider investing more in technologies such as smart meters, online billing, and mobile applications to improve its operational efficiency for the benefit of all stakeholders in this century.

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